

MESS 0001

MIMS 1.04 & 1.05: the EPEMC test

[And, introducing the MESS series]

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Re: Is EPEMC a “good” MIMS?

From the Desk of Sf. Ramon Careaga, founder EPEMC, www.epemcgateway.com

Dear Readers,

There is an interesting question that arises when we ask if extended plasma-electromagnetic cosmology, the open-source cosmology based upon cross-disciplinary utility and the firm mytho-historical and scientifico-historical *facts* of plasma, electric, and magnetic cosmologies, and birthed the Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual philosophy (which was shown to be self-consistent¹) is itself also a MIMS? Moreover, we find a need to produce many more mimsical analyses that enable cross analysis between the cosmology, philosophy, and the SPACERS² movement, as well as deal (of course) with the Strategy Series. The reason we need these opportunities is because modern strategy relies both upon the 0th Domain³ (technology), which itself uses electricity, but also upon a SPACERS related top down strategy of warfare. Literally: space and cyberspace becomes the domains where modern warfare has teeth *first*, before the typical air, land, and sea. Both are reliant- heavily - not on Big Bang and Dark Universe cosmologies, which have literal relation to reality, and almost no utility in these regards - but upon plasma, electricity, and magnetism. These are the foundational items of PEMC and EPEMC, both. The former, being wholly scientific, needs no philosophical analysis, and after all the scientific method is itself a classic MIMS (2.1)⁴. To “solve” the **mess** mankind is in, we need a cosmology and a philosophy for the future. As Elon Musk put it,

Elon Musk ✓
@elonmusk

A new philosophy of the future is needed. I believe it should be curiosity about the Universe – expand humanity to become a multiplanet, then interstellar, species to see what’s out there.

11:38 AM · Jul 27, 2022 · Twitter for iPhone

17.2K Retweets 3,779 Quote Tweets 164.3K Likes

Figure 1 - Elon Musk tweet; credit: twitter.com⁵

MIMS 1.04 - EPEMC as a MIMS

The three main standards of the MIMS are:

1. Futurization
2. Improving Human Potential, Energy, and Momentum (the Nikola Tesla Gold Standard)
3. Improving human-nature interface with an emphasis on improving the environment (while not eliminating the egalitarian humanism⁶ and freedom⁷ of the *true* liberal world).

The main hypotheses that are central to the MIMS is summed up in “MIMS 2+” paper:

“The MIMS is not at all clarified but there are several useful hypotheses that come from a loose

¹ Literally futurizing, as well as producing of life-producing ideas, promoting health and harmony of mankind with Nature, etc. https://www.academia.edu/53713967/MIMS_1_12_Self_Consistency_of_the_Big_G_Diagram

² SPACERS is a movement *and a standard*: <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/spacers>

³ https://www.academia.edu/67829412/Technology_as_the_0th_War_Domain

⁴ https://www.academia.edu/50804855/MIMS_2_Applications_discussions

⁵ <https://twitter.com/elonmusk/status/1552317587694010368?lang=en>

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https://www.academia.edu/38206009/Parameterization_of_New_Religion_utilizing_EPEMC_and_Western_Humanistic_Egalitarianism_as_a_guide

⁷ www.freeth.us

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philosophical analysis (that was done on the fly), and which warrant some form of testing in an engineering or Operations Research capacity:

- I. Use the scientific method and contain the infinite and the definite.*
- II. There may exist an unknown inversion of behavior property in moderating the F and N powers - the Force and Numbers, respectively.*
- III. The more trials of the system the more likely the system is to hit upon good, actionable data and results.*
- IV. Use metrics and analytics and look for more means to innovate, not less.*
- V. paying too much attention to what others do/say will cause a MIMS to lose focus and potency (Distraction hypothesis).*
- VI. If a MIMS does not perform, it is not mediating the motion from spiritual to material and vice versa" (p.23).*

In reaction to point 1, this is another self-consistency issue. An open-source standard, which avoids the peer-review cult and presents the data directly to the public and science peers via social media is a hallmark of EPEMC. In point 2 there is a clear motive of the EPEMC to encourage taking advantage of the human potential to solve the problems (it creates, science or not), particularly in works such as "Conquering the Solar System"⁸, and the Strategy Series. Also, there are standards within the EPEMC, such as the Evidence Heat Map, and naming conventions, etc. which provide organizational framework for scale and growth⁹. These improve the use and efficiency of human thinking, to the point that papers are now interacting with the shows¹⁰, and a "think tank" like effect (such as "The Pulse"¹¹ and "AIM"¹²) is becoming super commonplace. Even exact phrases, quotes, and themes are synchronistically - as if via *quantum mechanics*¹³ - occurring while working on EPEMC papers *with* other members of the community saying nearly the exact same phraseology or speaking on the same topic!

Finally, in point 3 there is definitely room for direct improvement (the papers are stored on the *cloud*, after all.) However, there's a useful fact that EPEMC is **not at all** against the improvement of human-nature interactions. It is, more specifically, interested in the responsible leveraging of virgin resources, charge, and atomic material for the purposes of improving SPACERS' likelihood of success. Still, more EPEMC involvement in the discussion of permaculture etc. could be warranted, and any criticisms thus far are fair, if perhaps not genuinely spirited. There is nothing overt about electrogeological research that improves human-nature interactions, *however* those who are interested in these natural phenomenon tend also (like the author's work on the Hidden Destinations in Kentucky Project¹⁴) to promote direct involvement and 'in the field' study, of history, myth¹⁵, and the environment. As well as preservation¹⁶. Similarly, most of those in the EPEMC community care far more for nature than the so-called *environmentalists*, and certainly E. Musk with his insistence upon lithium battery infrastructure¹⁷!

⁸ https://www.academia.edu/62757621/Conquering_the_Solar_System

⁹ Cross-thread to AIM™ business standard.

¹⁰ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/home/shows>

¹¹ <https://rumble.com/c/c-1498071>

¹² AIM - Advanced Idea Mechanics - Planning Document

¹³ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/quantum>

¹⁴ www.hiddendestinationsky.com

¹⁵ See: Ancient Kentucke Historical Association

¹⁶ The HDKP utilizes preservation in its scoring systems.

¹⁷

<https://www.reuters.com/article/us-tesla-electric-germany/tesla-ceo-says-electric-cars-will-double-global-electricity-demand-idUSKBN28B5Q8>

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Quickly, in response to the hypotheses:

1. Done, potential true (the papers are never ending), and definitely true (no paper lasts forever).
2. Irrelevant for the paper, however, EPEMC as a cosmology framework is certainly capable of assessing new and unique physics. EU, by contrast, tends to reject non-classical physics¹⁸, almost to the point of throwing the baby out with the bathwater. EPEMC has no biases in this regard.
3. Again the standards and especially naming standards encourages this behavior. There are even 3rd eddy papers [X.Y.Z.A] which encourage depth. Thus far the depth of potential exploration is 7! or 5,040 explorations¹⁹.
4. "Give me data or give me death." Has any other philosophy held to an ORDA²⁰ standard?
5. While EPEMC does a lot of altstream *and* mainstream critique, and highly warranted one might add, it is not a skeptic centered cosmology, and comes off as less whiney or pedantic²¹ than other altstream cosmogonies²², as well as puts more teeth to the criticisms²³. Particularly through the use of exact timestamps²⁴, and not vague attacks²⁵. It does, however, enable sharp, even brutal attacks such as POS Theory²⁶, which can be used to make much more useful *thrusts and parries* in interactions with the toxic²⁷ and **dangerous**²⁸ mainstream.
6. EPEMC does nothing - nothing - except perform. From predicting the mainstream's switch to Charged Dark Matter²⁹ pseudoscience, to providing tools³⁰, figures & tables³¹, to engineering movements and standards, and finding various smoking guns^{32 33}... the framework has always performed³⁴ *and more*

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https://www.academia.edu/73271902/Paradigm_Shift_Comparison_EPEMC_vs_The_Rest_Comparing_PEMC_EU_PU_MU_and_SM_BSM

¹⁹ Hence MESS 0001 with 4 orders of magnitude; but that makes a total potential of 15,039 papers just in MIMS alone.

²⁰ Operations Research/Data Analytics

²¹ https://www.academia.edu/53139271/Strong_Letter_Response_to_Mr_Ben_Davidson_Suspicious_Observers_et_al

²² https://www.academia.edu/77978879/Theoria_Apophasis_the_Ken_Wheeler_Effect

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https://www.academia.edu/38105102/The_Dark_Matter_Scatter_How_the_Dark_Universe_Community_is_fraying_and_in_which_directions_as_a_response_to_the_DM_crisis_How_PEMC_re_unifies_the_camps

²⁴ https://www.academia.edu/63468751/Ashes_of_Atlantis_part_1

²⁵ Compare to the BS S. Crothers had to endure from a nobel Prize Winner!

https://www.academia.edu/68876325/Response_to_Crothers_Exposition_of_Unimodular_Defect

²⁶ https://www.academia.edu/77592483/MIMS_2_83_POS_Theory

²⁷ https://www.academia.edu/37706629/Drugs_Supplements_and_Complaints_2018_pdf

²⁸ le - the poison pushers

https://www.academia.edu/43190878/OPINION_On_Gurus_Electric_Universe_Predictions_Bio_electrics_Cometes_5G_and_Futurism

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https://www.academia.edu/37558537/The_Predictable_Rise_of_Charged_Dark_Matter_How_Covert_Matter_Hot_Grains_Plasma_in_Dark_Mode_is_pushing_the_failures_of_CDM_and_MOND_into_the_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Cosmological_Paradigm

³⁰ Matrix Multiplier & www.startergrower.com (extension: [dist \(2\).zip](#)) (howto:

<https://sites.google.com/view/resilientfirmintrasite/home/starter-grower>

³¹ https://www.academia.edu/63981900/EPEMC_Tables_and_Useful_Graphs_2019

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https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332831733_Proposed_Discovery_of_Perattian_Thunderbolt_of_the_Gods_Strike_Location_in_Versailles_KY_Comparison_of_Predicted_Models_and_LiDAR_scans_of_Big_Sink_location_in_Woodford_County_Addendum_for_Plasmaglyph

³³ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327424078_Great_Pyramids_of_Kentucky_-_Final

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https://www.academia.edu/37569958/EPEMC_tm_Benefits_Ten_Reasons_to_Consider_Switching_to_Extended_Plasma_electromagnetic_Cosmology

*importantly: evolved*³⁵. Recently it provided a strong backbone to the 2022 World EM Expo³⁶, and encouraged a new level of intergenerational cross-disciplinary gathering and mimsical interface. This while simultaneously expanding into business³⁷ and media markets with new business analytics³⁸ and frameworks³⁹, as well as live shows⁴⁰, podcasts, etc.

MIMS 1.05 - the MESS series

Introducing the MESS series:

- MIMS
- EPEMC
- SPACERS
 - ◆ Strategy⁴¹
- Shorts
 - ◆ Series

Figure 2 - MESS logo; credit: author.

The point is to make strange proposals, hypothetical musings and test options, wax philosophic (blatantly) on ORDA and other matters, without the hefty *gravity* of the **old guard**'s standards on dense, word heavy scientific papers. As compact, and interactive as possible, without making an overt

mess, with increased cross-fiber relational density and dual referential standards. This means directions that go from two, three, or even four interfaces, and in incredibly short spaces⁴²

MIMS 1.05.1 - MESS Standards

Briefly spoken:

Identify topic/problem → Define the t/p → Discuss and hypothesize, briefly (within a few pages or less) **(1)**

Be Bold	Be Honest
No Compromise for Integrity	Highly Potent but Beneficial to Humanity

Sincerely,
Sf. R. Careaga

³⁵ https://www.academia.edu/76126629/Switch_to_EPEMC_2

³⁶ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mU2fr9RJ_8

³⁷ [2022 EM World Expo - Shifu Ramon part 1 / Extended Plasma Electromagnetic Cosmology EPEMC](#)

³⁸ www.resilient-way.com & www.americanintegratedcircuit.com etc.

³⁸

³⁹ https://www.academia.edu/50901241/MIMS_2_1_1_2_Aether_Business_and_Analytics_With_a_short_reflection_upon_the_philosophies_of_Ayn_Rand_and_the_concepts_of_Fortune_as_it_relates_to_the_Aether

³⁹ https://www.academia.edu/76140647/MIMS_Aether_Flow_and_Business_Circuit_Theory

⁴⁰ www.leakproject.com

⁴¹ https://www.academia.edu/51643169/MIMS_2_6_2_Strategy_and_Dualism

⁴² Without resorting to Orwellian "newspeak" or internet |337 speech, emoticonistics and memology.